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Effect of employee recognition on employee retention in hotels in Kenya

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The aim of this research study was to find out the effect of employee recognition on employee retention in hotels in Kenya. The hotel industry in Kenya falls short of the industries turnover average and still leads in employee turnover. In the year 2011, labor turnover was at 68% in five star rated hotels. Today, the industry is confronted with the continuously evolving challenge of demand for retention of appropriate talent. Consequently, this has impacted negatively on hotel business sustainability due to high costs of training new employees, replacement and separation for the departing employees as well as affecting customer satisfaction. The objectives of the study were to establish the effect of career development on employee retention in the hotels in Kenya. This research problem was studied through the use of a survey research design. The target population of this study comprised of 213 hotels registered under the Kenya Association of Hotelkeepers and Caterers in Kenya. A representative sample of 137 hotels was selected from each hotel region using stratified random sampling. Data were collected using structured questionnaire administered by the researcher to get response from the sample population. A pilot test was

conducted to test the reliability and validity of the data collection instruments. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. The findings in the Deloitte correlation analysis indicated that employee recognition is positively and significantly associated with employee retention in the hotel industry in Kenya. From the univariate analysis, the study also found that employee recognition has a positive and significant influence on employee retention in the hotel industry in Kenya. The study recommended that the management of the hotels should enhance employee recognition through monthly or yearly recognition. The study concluded that employee recognition affects employee retention in the hotel industry in Kenya. There was a positive and significant relationship between employee recognition and employee retention in the hotel industry. This shows that when employee recognition in an organization increases, employee retention also increases and when employee recognition decreases, employee retention decreases.

Keywords: Employee recognition, employee retention, hotel industry

INTRODUCTION

Hotel industry plays a key role in the development of nation's economy (Duncan, 2005). According to Barky, (2006), a hotel is an establishment that provides lodging paid on a short-term basis. Bharwani and Butt, (2012) indicates that the provision of basic accommodation, in the past, consisting only of a room with a bed, a cupboard, a small table and a washstand has largely been

replaced by rooms with modern facilities, including en-suite bathrooms and air conditioning or climate control. Additional common features found in hotel rooms are a telephone, an alarm clock, a television, a safe, a mini-bar with snack foods and drinks, and facilities for making tea and coffee (Bharwani and Butt, 2012). Larger hotels may provide additional guest facilities such as a swimming

pool, fitness center, business center, childcare, conference facilities and social function services (Gu and Siu, 2009). Tourism and Hospitality industry has continued to receive rigorous attention of academics, business tycoons and economic analysts because of its growing effect on the GDP of a country (Uddin *et al.*, 2008). The hotel industry is a dynamic service sector where optimal human resource management is required to ensure professionalism and efficiency in service delivery (Hanzaee and Mirvaisi, 2011). As a result, it is challenging for the hospitality based organizations to recruit and develop potential service providers to provide better services to the domestic and international guests. As hospitality industry offers intangible services and products, effective human resource management (HRM) especially recruitment is critical to the success of the stated industry (Walker, 2004).

Employee retention is vital for the hospitality sector as it employs more people than any other industry within the private sector both domestically and globally (Ogbonna and Lloyd, (2002) Achieving employee retention entails effective leadership with long-term vision (Enderwick, 2011). Overcoming organizational challenges including employee retention requires the collaboration of academia (Olson, 2010), business sector (Cavico and Mujtaba, 2010), and the government (Molian, 2012). Employee retention is achievable if employees are equipped with the skills they need (Singh, 2012). The challenge is that today’s workers particularly the millennials have different perspectives than those from five or six decades ago (Solnet *et al.*, 2012). The millennial employees are unlikely to remain with the same company or industry for their entire careers. Top management ought to recognize this by acting proactively and retaining talented people (Parry and Kelliher, 2009; Solnet *et al.*, 2012). The hotel industry plays a fundamental and vital role in the growth of the Kenyan economy. A study carried out by Kuria *et al.* (2011) in Kenya revealed that labor turnover was at 68% in five star rated hotels. A high number of staff leaving an organization at any given period is detrimental to both the employees and the employer in terms of performance and efficiency. For instance, high loss of employees can make first time employees fresh from college to reduce, give rise to use of casual labour on temporary terms, affect negatively on output and sustainability, and hinders career progression.

At present, the hotel industry is faced with the endlessly developing challenges of demand for retention of appropriate talent and competitive employees on permanent and pensionable basis. Recruitment costs account for a tremendous proportion of hotel operation expenses. Deloitte’s report states that, ‘An average hotelier spends 45% of operating expenses and 33% of revenues on labour costs.’ High turnover rates cause extra overheads in recruitment and career development. According to the report 52% of the cost of recruiting

employees is productivity loss and 14% is on-boarding and career development.

Research carried out by Kuria *et al.*, (2011) in Kenya indicated that labor turnover was at 68% in five star rated hotels, the industry is confronted with the continuously evolving challenge of demand for retention of appropriate talent. Empirical studies have been conducted on employee retention in various sectors in Kenya. Onyango, (2014) conducted a study on the relationship between rewards and employee retention in Non-Governmental conservation organizations in Nairobi and established that work environment, learning and development, direct financial rewards and the indirect financial rewards had a positive correlation to employee retention.

The study focused on conservation NGOs and therefore it cannot be generalized to KAHC. Kimunge, (2014) did a study on Kenya Vision 2030 Delivery Secretariat, it was established that compensation, work-life balance, training and career growth have positive impact in employees’ decision to stay or leave an organization. However, a poor compensation structure and lack of career growth were seen to be the components that have the most profound impact on employee retention at Kenya Vision 2030 Delivery Secretariat. The study was limited to Kenya Vision 2030 secretariat; it did not address issues facing hotels registered by KAHC in Kenya.

This paper focused on hotels registered with the Hotel Keepers and Caterers Association in Kenya. The hotels are situated in regions which will be useful in ensuring that every hotel region is represented through stratified sampling. The research study will be limited to job promotion. The population of this study was 213 hotels registered with Hotelkeepers and Caterers Association in Kenya. The objective of the study is to determine how employee recognition affects employee retention in the hotel industry in Kenya.

Theoretical /conceptual framework

The study was guided by the following conceptual framework (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework.

A theoretical framework should demonstrate an understanding of theories and concepts that are relevant to the research topic (Labaree, 2013).

The theoretical review for this paper was based on Maslow's Needs Hierarchy Theory that explains the effect of career development on employee retention. Maslow, (1943) stated that people are motivated by the desire to achieve or maintain the various conditions upon which these basic satisfactions rest and by certain more intellectual desires as the average number of society is most often partially satisfied and partially unsatisfied in all of one's wants. Whittington and Evans, (2005), stated that Maslow presented a needs hierarchy in which at least five sets of needs compose the framework. The five sets of needs were divided into two categories: basic needs and higher-order needs. The most basic human needs, represented by food, water, shelter, and safety, are considered essential for human existence. Higher-order needs are those associated with social activities, esteem building, and self-actualization or constant self-improvement. Elaborating further on this theory, Whittington and Evans, (2005) stated that each of these needs operates at all times, although one deficient set dominates the individual at any one time and circumstance. Maslow's hierarchy is commonly displayed in a pyramid fashion, with the basic needs at the bottom and the higher needs at the top. The needs were depicted in this way to show the significance of each need on the others, with the most important and broadest category being the physiological needs at the base (Redmond, 2010). According to Maslow, (1943), higher order needs such as self-esteem or social needs should determine behavior only when lower needs are satisfied. This theory suggests that for managers to motivate employees, they need to devise programs or practices aimed at satisfying emerging or unmet needs since most of the lower needs are felt again and again (Kreitner, 2004). When the need hierarchy concept is applied to work organizations (Pearce, 2011), managers have the responsibility to create a proper climate in which employees can develop to their fullest potential (Hoisch, 2001). Failure to provide such a climate would theoretically decrease employee satisfaction and could result in poor performance, lower job satisfaction and increased withdrawal from the organization (Kremer and Hommond, 2013). Maslow's theory is linked to job promotion in that workers move up the pyramid during their employment experience and this helps them to stay longer in the organization because they feel self-actualized.

Employee recognition

Recognition means appreciation with a show of gratitude. When such appreciation is offered to the work performed by employees, they feel inspired to perform better and better. In the organizational atmosphere, status means the grading of positions, rights and duties in the formal organization structure the status system is an tool of motivation because it is tremendously significant for most

of the people. For this reason, status system should be closely related to the abilities and the aspirations of people on the organization (Wambugu and Ombui, 2013). Top performing employees are harder to come by and even harder to keep. Successful organizations recognize the importance of developing a recognition and reward program to recognize and validate the work of the employees. According to Uddin *et al.* (2008) these programs can be formal such as ones that offer material incentives for the employees who achieve predestined goals or informal such as providing of positive feedback such as verbal praise. Recognition of employee behavior is rooted in the psychology principle of positive reinforcement in that behavior that is rewarded is more likely to be repeated. Recognition of behavior that promotes the organizational goals has been shown to improve employee performance and retention (Sutherland, 2004).

Many employers however are hesitant to initiate recognition and reward programs and they dismiss them as high cost activities that bring little tangible benefits to the company and its employees. However, research shows that recognition that ranges from verbal praise and small non cash rewards can be a cost effective tool to raise the employees morale, lower stress, absenteeism and in the end lower employee turnover. In addition, while the employees benefit from these programs, the employer is also likely to benefit from increased employee productivity and decreased costs that are associated with turnover rates.

However individuals like to be recognized differently and employers should find out what their employees value most and customize recognition accordingly (Samuel and Chipunza, 2009). Employers must also avoid recognition mistakes such as not getting the facts right and recognizing the wrong person. The form of recognition should also fit the degree of achievement. Acknowledgement should also be tied to specific actions to help employees recognize exactly what they did right. Regular recognition of employees can have a significant impact on their level of engagement. Recognition enables employees to feel better about themselves and their employer. Research by the Gallup organization shows that companies with higher employee engagement yield high retention than companies with employees with low employee engagements (Poulston, 2008). When employees feel that their efforts are appreciate and acknowledged, they are more likely to stay, recognition can also cultivate dedication and loyalty to the company.

Employee retention

Pousa and Mathieu, (2010) define retention as an obligation to continue to do business or exchange with a particular organization on an ongoing basis. Retention is "customer liking, identification, commitment, trust, readiness to recommend, and repurchase intentions, with

the first four being emotional-cognitive retention constructs, and the last two being behavioral intentions. According to Latukha, (2011) retention is driven by several key factors, which ought to be managed congruently: organizational culture, strategy, pay and benefits philosophy and career development systems. Day, (2000) argued that if companies cannot retain their employees, the economic results could be devastating for an organization.

A substantial amount of value could potentially end up employed by a competitor, or become the competition. For organizations, the high cost of recruitment and selection, the lag and productivity loss during the assimilation period, the likely loss of business opportunity, poor customer relationship, and hidden cost of loss productivity have subsequently highlighted the importance of retaining committed employees as an aspect of survival for organizations. Employers seek to treat employees as valued assets who can be a source of competitive advantage through their commitment, trust, adaptability and high quality skills and knowledge. This empowerment should increase the competitiveness of the business. Lucas and Deery, (2004) concluded that by using commitment strategies, organizations had significantly higher performance and lower turnover, compared to those using control strategies.

Employee retention issues are emerging as the most critical workforce management challenges of the immediate future. Since the mid-1990s, scholarly research investigations have been focusing not only on determining why employees leave organizations but also concentrating on those factors positively influencing employees to stay with an organization (Hoisch, 2001), as well as the benefits associated with retaining tenured workers.

Effectively designed and well implemented employee retention programs that increase employee tenure more than pay for themselves through reduced turnover costs leads to increased productivity. The most notable among hotels' retention initiatives is compensation and benefits. Numerous studies have addressed the impact of employee compensation, rewards and recognition on turnover and retention (Walsh and Taylor, 2007). In terms of wages, a survey by Norris (2012) indicated that workforce in hotel are usually low paid, compared with government average wage, staff in hotel earns just about 73% of the whole industry average. Another survey conducted by Choy (2012) pointed out that hospitality employees' average annual salaried have been found to be about 16.5% to 31.6 % below than the hotel industry average and government average wage. Additionally, highly competitive wage system promotes employee commitment and thus results in the attraction and retention of a superior workforce.

Further survey noted that staff will remain with an organization as long as it serves their self-interest to do so better than the alternatives available to them

elsewhere (Gupta, 2012). Although several study investigated the compensation can strongly influenced the staff turnover rate, also several other research have indicated that compensation in the form of base or variable pay may not be sufficient to attract or retain staff. The most important retention predictors included intrinsic fulfillment and working conditions rather than monetary rewards were confirmed by Milman and Ricci, (2003). Moreover, the absence of opportunity for professional growth and development affects hotels' turnover rate and retention instead of compensation and work-life balance (Walsh and Taylor, 2007).

The literature on employee retention clearly explains that satisfied employees who are happy with their jobs are more devoted for doing a good job and look forward to improve their organizational customers' satisfaction. Mendez and Stander, (2010) further emphasizes that a company needs to invest in employee retention in order to be successful. Many studies have indicated that in today's rapidly moving dynamic, uncertain and highly competitive global markets, firms worldwide are facing major decisions and challenges in the global talent management (Schuler, 2011; Scullion *et al.*, 2010; Tarique and Schuler, 2010).

As a result of a highly competitive market, companies are discovering that, not only is it becoming increasingly difficult to recruit top talent, but that they are running the constant risk of losing the ones they have to competitors (Sutherland, 2004). According to Kumar, (2012), Indian software industries face crises in various retention and attrition strategies of talented workers. The authors examined the phenomenon if employee retention in the IT sector can help organizations to retain their variable talented employees. The study concluded that HR department has to play a vital role in design policies and strategies that enable the organizations to retain the human resources contributing significantly to the business. Eric *et al.* (2012) studied how employees regard the importance of their empowerment, equity of compensation, job design through training and expectancy toward effective performance management on their retention. It was found that training and development, performance management and compensation are significant to employee retention. Further, numerous studies explain the importance of high employees 'involvement and how it could enhance their retention. In summary, the literature defines retention as continuing relation between employees and their organization.

Empirical studies

Numerous studies have addressed the impact of employee compensation, rewards and recognition on turnover and retention (Walsh and Taylor, 2007). Bartlomiejczuk, (2015) conducted a study on how

recognition programs impact employee engagement and how have companies with a large global footprint structured such programs to drive results. The results indicated that employee engagement is now the largest concern of many companies' HR departments and it is widely suspected that recognition has an important role to play in fostering engagement. While recognition is not new, it is finally becoming more strategic as programs align recognition with business objectives and desired behaviours.

Tessema et al. (2013) carried out a study on the effects of employee recognition, pay, and benefits on job satisfaction. In this cross-sectional study, survey responses from university students in the US, Malaysia and Vietnam were analyzed. Employee recognition was found to have a significant impact on job satisfaction, regardless of home country income level (high, middle or low income) and culture (collectivist or individualist). However, the effect of employee recognition on job satisfaction was significantly more important for US respondents than for respondents from Malaysia and Vietnam. Nolan and Sara (2008) in their research study on current trends in talent management emphasized critical recognition as one of the main topics for developing and retaining the best employees and enabling organizations.

Rizwan, (2010) suggested that the Human Resources are the most important among all the resources an organization owns, and to retain efficient and experienced workforce in an organization is very crucial in overall performance of an organization. The results showed that different dimensions of work motivation and satisfaction are significantly correlated. It also displayed that reward and employee recognition has great impact on the motivation of the employees and their intention to stay with the organization. Kyndt *et al.* (2009) focused on the organizational and personal factors that influence employee retention. The study found that a large positive contribution of recognition and stimulation of the employee to employee retention. Bartlomiejczuk (2015) found that employee recognition was positively related to employee engagement: 41% of the variation in employee engagement is attributable to the strength of recognition an employee receives. A research study by Corporate Leadership Council (2009) indicated that approximately 90% of companies maintain some type of reward and recognition program. The majority of companies use these programs to create a positive work environment, improve employee morale, and motivate high performance. Research suggests that when designed and implemented properly, reward and employee recognition positively affects an organization's bottom line. Although reward and recognition programs have the potential to produce positive returns to shareholders, research demonstrates that such benefits will only be achieved through an effective program that reinforces an organization's goals and values in a well publicized,

thoughtful program affecting a large number of employees.

Khan et al. (2011) conducted a study on the effects of recognition-based rewards on employees' efficiency and effectiveness. For the purpose of study a close ended questionnaire was used to infer the relation between supervisors' recognition (independent variable) and employees' performance, their desire to remain with the organization, and their long term effectiveness in within the organization etc. (dependent variables). Al-Karam Towel Industries Limited Karachi was selected for the study where at sample size of 100 employees was opted for. The effect of supervisory recognition on employees was examined using Chi-squared test. The study found that employee recognition-based rewards on employees' efficiency and effectiveness.

The study research gap was demonstrated by lack of empirical studies on reward management practices that affect retention of employees in the hotel industry in Kenya. Empirical studies Kimunge, (2014), Onyango, (2014) and Wanderi et al. (2011) were inadequate as they concentrated on other sectors. None of these studies undertook a study on the hotels registered under the hotel keepers and caterers association in Kenya. Therefore this study sought to address this gap by undertaking an empirical study on the effects of job promotion on employee retention in hotels that are registered with the hotel keepers and caterers association

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey design method was employed in this study. Descriptive research design is appropriate when the objective is to determine the degree of the relatedness of the variables (Elahi and Dehdashti, 2011). The population of this study was 213 hotels registered with Hotelkeepers and Caterers Association in Kenya. The sample population was 137 hotels. The sampling frame for this study was all the regions in Kenya. These include Coast, Malindi Watamu, Mount Kenya, Nairobi, Rift Valley, Western and Nyanza and Amboseli Tsavo. The sample size for this study was determined using the sample table developed by Krejcie and Morgan formula developed in 1970 as shown in appendix two (Research Advisors, 2006). It is common practice for most studies for the confidence level to be at 95% and a precision +/- 5% (Turner, 2003; Gupta, 2012). The population for this study is 213 therefore the sample size at 95% confidence level was 137 hotel managers. The study used stratified random sampling with a proportional allocation of each stratum. Stratified sampling is used for data which does not constitute a homogenous group but that which is heterogeneous. Proportionate stratification was used to select the sample size per hotel region. In proportionate stratification, a random sample from each stratum is taken

Table 1. Sample size.

Hotel Regions	Population	Sample size	Percentage
Coast	46	30	22
Malindi Watamu	15	10	7.4
Mount Kenya	24	15	11.7
Nairobi	54	35	25
Rift Valley	54	35	25
Western& Nyanza	4	2	1.5
Amboseli	16	10	7.3
Total	213	137	100

Table 2. Number of employees per hotel.

	Frequency	Percent
Less than 100	51	43.6
101 to 200	33	28.2
201 to 300	11	9.4
301 to 400	9	7.7
401 to 500	6	5.1
501 to 600	1	.9
601 to 700	2	1.7
701 to 800	1	.9
801 to 900	3	2.6
Total	117	100.0

in a number proportional to the stratum's size when compared to the population (Greener, 2008). These strata subsets are then pooled to form a random sample. Questionnaires were administered to 137 human resource managers who are registered with KHAC in 2015. This paper collected data by use of questionnaires. The questionnaires were then administered through a drop and pick later method, this technique is an effective means to reduce potential non-response bias through increased response rate (Table 1).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the results of this paper, 47.9% of the human resource managers indicated that they were aged between 31 and 40 years, 39.3% indicated that they were aged between 41 and 50 years, 8.5% indicated that they were aged between 51 and 60 years and 4.3% indicated that they were aged between 21 and 30 years as indicated. This shows that most of the respondents (human resource managers) were aged between 31 and 50 years. Out of 117 responses that were obtained, 71.8% (84) were from male respondents while 28.2% (33) were from female respondents. The paper also sought to establish the classification of the hotels involved in this study as indicated. From the findings, 45.3% of the human resource managers indicated that their hotels were five stars, 35% indicated four stars and 17.1% indicated three stars. Also, 1.7% indicated that their hotels were six stars and 0.9% indicated that their hotels were seven stars. This shows that most of the hotels sampled in this study were five stars and four

stars. From the findings, 43.6% (51) of the hotels had less than 100 staff, 28.2% had between 101 and 200 staff and 9.4% had between 201 and 300 staff. In addition, 0.9% (1) of the human resource managers indicated that their hotels had between 501 and 600 staff and the same percent had between 701 and 800 staff. It is only 2.6% (3) hotels that had between 801 and 900 staff. The paper also sought to find out the number of years the hotels had been existing. The results show that 29.9% of the hotels had been in existence for between 12 and 23 years. In addition, the same percent of the hotels (29.9%) had been in existence for between 24 and 35 years. Only 5.1% of the hotels had been in existence for between 48 and 59 years. Also, 17.9% had been in existence for below 11 years. These findings clearly indicate that most of the hotels in Kenya have been in existence for between 12 and 35 years (Table 2).

Findings on the influence of employee recognition on employee retention

This paper found out that the respondents suggested that the influence of employee recognition on employee retention in the hotel industry in Kenya. The results in (Table 3); indicate that the respondents agreed with a mean of 4.427 and a standard deviation of 0.710 that employee recognition in their hotels is accompanied with some rewards. The respondents also agreed with a mean of 4.427 and a standard deviation of 0.769 that their employers offer appreciation for the job well done. The respondents further agreed with a mean of 4.367 and a standard deviation of 0.867 that their employers provide

Table 3. Employee recognition

	SD %	D %	N %	A %	SA %	Mean	Std. Deviation
My employer offers appreciation for the job well done	0	3.4	6.8	33.3	56.4	4.427	0.769
My employer involves us in decision making	2.6	6.8	17.1	26.5	47	4.085	1.071
Employee recognition comes with increase in responsibility	0	6	7.7	30.8	55.6	4.359	0.865
My employer provides opportunities to get high positions	0.9	4.3	7.7	31.6	55.6	4.367	0.867
Employee recognition is accompanied with some rewards	0	2.6	5.1	39.3	53	4.427	0.710

Table 4. Model summary for employee recognition and employee retention.

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
0.591	0.350	0.344	0.32684

opportunities to get high positions. These findings agree with Msengeti and Obwogi, (2015) that the hotels were giving good recognition for satisfactory work and there were adequate opportunities to use their personal talents and use their initiatives. Further, the respondents agreed with a mean of 4.359 and a standard deviation of 0.865 that employee recognition in their hotels comes with increase in responsibility (Table 3). In addition, the respondents agree with a mean of 4.085 and a standard deviation of 1.071 that their employers involve them in decision making. Recognition refers to the extent to which employees perceive recognition (e.g. promotions, verbal recognition, awards) to be effective and fairly implemented within the organization (Table 3). These findings are in line with Zaitouni et al. (2011) monetary compensation is important, but not sufficient to retain employees. Recognition in the form of non-monetary elements (e.g. verbal recognition and positive feedback) is also important. Paré and Tremblay, (2007) indicate that recognition from managers and peers has been found to be related to affective and continuance commitment. From the findings, the respondents suggested that the management of the hotels should enhance recognition through employees of the month or of the year recognition. In addition, the respondents suggested that recognition should go in hand with a good gain in finance and not just certificates and trophies. Further, the respondents suggested that the management should entail other skills or talents of

employees and recognize them. For instance, sports music, drama activities.

Employee recognition and employee retention

The results in Table 4, on model summary reveal that, the R-squared for the relationship between employee recognition (X_4) and employee retention was 0.344, which shows that employee recognition can explain 34.4% of the dependent variable (employee retention) variation. The R square value is an important indicator of the predictive accuracy of the equation. The remaining 65.6% can be explained by other factors in relation to employee

retention in the hotel industry. The implication of these findings is that employee recognition plays a significant role in enhancing employee retention. The study used ANOVA to establish the significance of the regression model. In testing the significance level, the statistical significance was considered significant if the p-value was less or equal to 0.05. The significance of the regression model is shown in the below with P-value of 0.00 which is less than 0.05. This indicates that the regression model is statistically significant in predicting the effect of employee recognition on employee retention in Kenya. Basing the confidence level at 95% the analysis indicates high reliability of the results obtained. The Anova results shown in (Table 5) depict that; the F-critical (1, 115) was 3.92 while the F-calculated was 61.835. This shows that F-calculated was greater than the F-critical and hence there is a linear relationship between the two variables (employee recognition and employee retention). This implies that when there is an increase in employee recognition there is a significant increase in employee retention. In addition, the p-value was 0.000, which was less than the significance level (0.05). This confirms goodness of fit of the model in predicting the influence of employee recognition (X_4) on employee retention.

Regression coefficients for employee recognition and employee retention

Using the unstandardized coefficients the following equation applies: $Y = 2.395 + 0.397X_4$.

The results in Table 6 indicate that employee retention will be having an index of 2.395 when employee recognition (X_4) is held constant. In addition, the Beta coefficient (β_4) was 0.397. This shows that a unit increase in employee recognition (X_4) would lead to a 0.397 increase in employee retention. In addition, the t calculated (7.864) is greater than the t critical (1.645), the relationship is significant as the P-value (0.000) was less than the significance level (0.05). Therefore the alternative hypothesis was accepted and concluded that "there is a positive significant relationship between employee recognition and employee retention in the hotel industry in Kenya".

Table 5. ANOVA for employee recognition and employee retention.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	6.605	1	6.605	61.835	0.000
Residual	12.285	115	0.107		
Total	18.890	116			

Table 6. Regression coefficients for employee recognition and employee retention.

	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficient	t	Sig.
	β	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.395	0.225		10.662	0.000
Employee recognition	0.397	0.050	0.591	7.864	0.000

Table 7. Statements on employee retention in the hotel industry.

	SD %	D %	N %	A %	SA %	Mean	Std. Deviation
My employer encourages staff to work longer in the hotel	0.9	4.3	40.2	30.8	23.9	3.726	0.906
Staff retrenchment takes place every year	4.3	22.2	63.2	8.5	1.7	2.812	0.718
Some staff leave the hotel voluntarily	1.7	20.5	52.1	19.7	6	3.076	0.842
Many staff leave the hotel involuntarily	3.4	23.1	50.4	16.2	6.8	3.000	0.9
Staff redundancy takes place every year in the hotel	5.1	24.8	54.7	11.1	4.3	2.846	0.847

Table 8. Annual employee retention descriptive statistics.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Number of employees in the hotel at the beginning of the year 2015	109	20	915	193.39	181.477
Number of employees at the end of the year in 2015	116	15	887	188.66	177.776
Number of employees who left the hotel involuntarily in 2015	29	0	20	5.79	5.728
Number of employees who left the hotel voluntarily in 2015	30	0	11	4.40	2.774

In the study of Tizazu, (2015), recognition has a positive and significant effect on employee retention with a beta value (beta = 0.243), at 99% confidence level ($p < 0.01$) These findings concur with previous studies that also confirm a positive and significant relationship between recognition and employee retention (Fogleman and McCorkle, 2013 and Edirisooriya, 2014). The implication of these findings is that players in the hotel industry in Kenya should enhance employee recognition in order to achieve employee retention.

Employee retention in the hotel industry

In relation to employee retention, the respondents agreed with a mean of 3.726 and a standard deviation of 0.906 that their employers encourage staff to work longer in the hotel. However, the respondents were neutral on the statement indicating that staff retrenchment takes place every year in their hotels, as shown by a mean of 2.812 and a standard deviation of 0.718. In addition, the respondents were neutral on the statement that staff redundancy takes place every year in their hotels as a shown by a mean of 2.846 and a standard deviation of 0.847. Further, the respondents were neutral on the

statement indicating that some staffs leave their hotels voluntarily as indicated by a mean of 3.076 and a standard deviation of 0.842. Also, the respondents were neutral on the statement indicating that many staffs leave their hotel involuntarily as shown by a mean of 3.000 and a standard deviation of 0.900 (Table 7). From the findings, the average number of employees in the hotel industry at the beginning of the year 2015 was 193 per hotel, but at the end of the year in 2015 the hotel industry had an average 188 employees per hotel. In addition, an average of 5 staff left the hotels involuntarily in 2015 while an average of 4 staff left the hotel voluntarily in 2015. This shows that an average of 10 staff in every hotel had left their hotels in the year 2015 (Table 8). Employee retention refers to the ability of an organization to retain its employees. Employee retention rate is obtained by dividing the number of employees that remain in an organization at the end of the year with the total number of employees.

Conclusion

In the descriptive statistics, majority of the respondents indicated that employee recognition in their hotels was accompanied by some rewards, their employers offer

appreciation for the job well done and their employers provide opportunities to get high positions. The study also found that employee recognition in hotels in Kenya comes with increase in responsibility and their employers involve them in decision making. The findings in the correlation analysis indicated that employee recognition is positively and significantly associated with employee retention in the hotel industry in Kenya. The study also established that employee recognition is positively associated with career development, remuneration and job promotion. From the univariate analysis, the study also found that employee recognition has a positive and significant influence on employee retention in the hotel industry in Kenya. The study also established that hotel rating moderates the effect of employee recognition on employee retention in the hotel industry in Kenya. Appreciation is a fundamental human need. Employees respond to appreciation expressed through recognition of their good work because it confirms their work is valued. When employees and their work are valued, their satisfaction and productivity rises, and they are motivated to maintain or improve their good work. Praise and recognition are essential to an outstanding workplace. People want to be respected and valued for their contribution. Everyone feels the need to be recognized as an individual or member of a group and to feel a sense of achievement for work well done or even for a valiant effort. Everyone wants a 'pat on the back' to make them feel good. The study concluded that employee recognition affects employee retention in the hotel industry in Kenya. There was a positive and significant relationship between employee recognition and employee retention in the hotel industry. This shows that when employee recognition in an organization increases, employee retention also increases and when employee recognition decreases, employee retention decreases. Lastly, the study concluded that the moderating effect of hotel rating was significant between the reward management practices and employee retention.

Recommendations

Employee recognition should be clear and well communicated to the staff. The criteria should outline clearly the stand of the institution on internal promotions versus the external appointments. The policy should be revised to make it all inclusive so that it is not skewed in favor of some duties while ignoring others and also to reflect fairness. The management of the hotels should enhance employee recognition through a monthly or yearly recognition. In addition, recognition should be accompanied by some financial rewards or job promotion and not just certificates and trophies.

Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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